

Audience and voter education

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In a few weeks, communication strategies for the upcoming presidential and assembly elections in Ecuador will formally begin. Messages of changes and improvements will be heard in order to position the candidates. This is what happens before each election, and there is always the expectation of the fulfilment of the offers.

Interviews and interactions will multiply to consolidate the contenders. Some people are already publicly known and may have an advantage, but well-conducted marketing will ensure that even controversial issues will win preferences.

Faced with the need for critical consumption of media content in election campaigns, there is an insistence on citizen education by political parties and organisations, hand in hand with the regulatory authorities, but there is no sustained process.

There are civic groups and NGOs that develop projects, such as training schools, which require partners to continue, but these initiatives are intermittent and do not lead to public service trajectories.

There is a need to articulate the will of leaders to sustain permanent spaces of popular civic awareness that will get responsible audiences, based on their competencies, to critically read the advertisements that circulate in the campaigns. It is a task that summons voters, from the guidance of politicians.

The National Electoral Council of Ecuador, civil society and some parties should be joined by the majority of Ecuadorians who aspire to positive developments, and know that one of the first actions is to assume the right to vote.